

DataTools4Heart

A European Health Data Toolbox for Enhancing Cardiology Data Interoperability, Reusability and Privacy

Milestone MS16: Deep Learning based clinical computational semantics and concept recognition systems

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Executive Summary

This report presents the progress achieved in the development of deep learning-based clinical computational semantics and concept recognition systems within the DataTools4Heart (DT4H) project. The work focuses on two main components: (i) multilingual pretrained clinical language models adapted to the cardiology domain, and (ii) advanced Named Entity Recognition (NER) systems for the extraction of clinically relevant concepts from unstructured Electronic Health Records (EHRs).

Building upon previous milestones, particularly the development of multilingual corpora (MS8) and domain-adapted language models (MS5), this milestone reports on the integration and progressive refinement of these resources into downstream semantic extraction pipelines. A key aspect of this work has been the iterative improvement of both the quantity and quality of the available multilingual clinical data, enabling increasingly robust and accurate automatic information extraction.

Specifically, the consortium has:

- Developed and refined multilingual clinical language models across the seven project languages, leveraging domain-adaptive pretraining strategies and progressively larger and higher-quality datasets.
- Designed and trained deep learning-based NER systems capable of identifying cardiology-relevant entities (e.g., disorders, symptoms, procedures, drugs) from clinical text.
- Iteratively improved model performance through continuous data enrichment, annotation refinement, and integration of synthetic and translated corpora.
- Evaluated the impact of domain adaptation and data scaling on downstream tasks, showing consistent improvements in entity recognition performance.

Overall, the results highlight a clear progression in system performance driven by the expansion and refinement of multilingual clinical resources. These advances demonstrate the feasibility of scalable, multilingual clinical Natural Language Processing (NLP) pipelines and represent a key step toward high-quality structured data extraction and interoperability in European cardiology data systems.

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Acronyms

Barcelona Supercomputing Center: BSC

Beginning–Inside–Outside: BIO

Cardiology Clinical Case Corpus: CardioCCC

DataTools4Heart: DT4H

Electronic Health Records: EHR

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources: FHIR

Masked-language modelling: MLM

Milestone: MS

Named Entity Recognition: NER

Natural Language Processing: NLP

Natural Language Processing – Common Data Model: NLP-CDM

Next Sentence Prediction - NSP

Original Native Clinical Case Corpus: OnaCCC

Parallel CLInical Text: ParaCliTe

Spanish Clinical Case Corpus: SpaCCC

Work Package: WP

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1 Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases remain one of the main causes of morbidity and mortality in Europe and represent a major burden for healthcare systems, research infrastructures and public health planning. Across European hospitals and clinical centres, large volumes of cardiovascular health data are generated every day through routine care, diagnostic procedures, treatment follow-up and long-term patient monitoring. These data constitute a highly valuable resource for improving clinical research, supporting evidence-based care, enabling secondary use of health data and advancing data-driven innovation in cardiology.

However, the reuse of cardiovascular health data across institutions and countries is still limited by several technical and organisational barriers. Clinical data are often stored in heterogeneous formats, follow different local documentation practices and are described using different languages, coding systems and levels of structure. This fragmentation makes it difficult to compare, integrate and analyse data across sites, limiting the potential of European cardiovascular data for research, clinical decision support and health innovation. The DataTools4Heart project addresses this challenge by developing a European cardiology data toolbox aimed at improving the interoperability, reusability, quality and privacy-preserving use of cardiovascular health data.

A particularly important challenge concerns EHRs, which have become one of the main sources of clinical information in healthcare systems. EHRs capture rich and detailed information about patient histories, diagnoses, symptoms, procedures, treatments, test results and clinical findings. Nevertheless, a substantial part of this clinically meaningful information is not available in structured fields. Instead, it is embedded in unstructured free-text narratives, such as discharge summaries, clinical notes, progress reports, referral letters or imaging reports. Without dedicated text processing and NLP methods, this information remains difficult to access automatically and cannot be fully exploited by downstream applications such as cohort identification, epidemiological studies, clinical decision support or cross-site cardiovascular research.

NLP provides a key technological layer for transforming unstructured clinical text into structured and reusable information. Within clinical NLP, NER systems are especially relevant, as they allow the automatic identification and classification of clinically meaningful mentions in free text. These mentions may refer, for example, to diseases, symptoms, procedures, medications or other relevant biomedical concepts. When these extracted entities are further linked to controlled medical terminologies such as SNOMED CT, ICD-10 or other standard vocabularies, they can support semantic interoperability and contribute to the creation of structured clinical data models suitable for reuse across institutions.

In the European context, the development of clinical NLP systems is further complicated by linguistic diversity. While much of the clinical NLP landscape has historically focused on English, European healthcare institutions operate across many languages, each with its own terminology, morphology, clinical documentation style and availability of annotated resources. This situation is particularly relevant for DataTools4Heart, which addresses cardiology data across seven languages: English, Spanish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Swedish and Czech. Building robust clinical concept recognition systems in this setting requires multilingual resources, domain-adapted language models, language-specific evaluation strategies and mechanisms for dealing with low-resource scenarios.

Within DataTools4Heart, Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on the multilingual standardisation of structured and unstructured health data. This work package provides the methodological and technical basis for processing clinical narratives across languages and transforming them into structured semantic annotations. Previous activities in WP3, particularly MS5, established cardiology-adapted language models for the seven consortium languages through domain-adaptive pretraining. These models provide

multilingual and domain-aware representations of cardiovascular clinical text and constitute a foundation for more advanced downstream NLP tasks (see Figure 1).

MS16 builds directly on this foundation and represents a transition from language model adaptation towards operational clinical report recognition. The milestone focuses on the development and evaluation of clinical semantics models for extracting relevant information from unstructured EHR text. This includes baseline approaches, such as string matching or fuzzy matching, as well as deep learning-based NER systems that use the cardiology-adapted language models developed in previous WP3 work. The main objective is to identify clinically relevant mentions in cardiology narratives and classify them into high-impact semantic categories aligned with the DataTools4Heart use cases, including diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications.

Figure 1: Overall workflow of Work Package 3 for multilingual standardisation of cardiology data in DataTools4Heart.

By developing this extraction layer, MS16 contributes to the broader DataTools4Heart data structuring and interoperability pipeline. The entities recognised by the NER systems provide a first structured representation of information originally contained in free-text clinical documentation. This structured output can then support subsequent processing steps such as terminology mapping, concept normalization and harmonization within the DT4H NLP-CDM/FHIR-oriented profile. In this way, MS16 establishes an essential bridge between multilingual unstructured EHR narratives and the downstream semantic interoperability components required for scalable cardiovascular data reuse across Europe.

2 Objectives of the Milestone

DataTools4Heart aims to develop a European cardiology data toolbox that improves the interoperability, reusability, quality and privacy-preserving use of cardiovascular health data. Within this framework, one of the central challenges addressed by the project is the transformation of heterogeneous and multilingual clinical information into structured, standardised and reusable data. This is particularly relevant for EHRs, where a large amount of clinically meaningful information is not available in structured fields but is instead

embedded in free-text narratives such as discharge summaries, clinical notes, progress reports or referral letters. The DataTools4Heart project therefore combines Common Data Model development, data ingestion and harmonization tools, multilingual NLP, federated learning, data synthesis and virtual assistant technologies to support cross-site and cross-language reuse of cardiology data.

Within the overall project objectives, WP3 focuses specifically on the multilingual standardisation of structured and unstructured health data. WP3 is directly linked to the project objective of introducing a multilingual NLP suite for cardiology, including cardiology-specific entity recognition and machine translation, to support the standardised structuring of cardiology reports across European regions. The expected outcomes of this objective include seven language models adapted to the cardiology domain, multilingual clinical corpora, semantic interoperability resources, unsupervised semantic annotation systems for low-resource languages, and deep learning-based clinical concept recognition systems for the seven project languages using active learning and clinician-in-the-loop annotation scenarios.

More specifically, WP3 defines two objectives that are directly relevant to this milestone: Objective 3.1 addresses the design of language models and tools for the automatic processing and translation of cardiology texts, while Objective 3.2 focuses on the development of systems for recognising clinical concepts in unstructured EHR data across different languages, and on their harmonization through mapping to controlled medical terminologies in order to generate structured clinical data models. These two objectives establish the technical path followed in this milestone: first, the creation and refinement of multilingual clinical language models; and second, the use of those models in downstream clinical concept recognition pipelines.

This milestone represents a key transition within WP3, moving from the development of multilingual clinical language resources and cardiology-adapted language models towards their use in operational semantic extraction systems. In this sense, the milestone builds directly on the outcomes of MS5, which established a family of cardiology-adapted language models for the seven consortium languages: English, Spanish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Swedish and Czech. Through domain-adaptive pretraining, these models were refined to better capture the lexical, syntactic and contextual characteristics of medical and cardiovascular narratives, including specialised terminology, domain-specific expressions and the stylistic conventions commonly found in EHRs. This previous work provided the multilingual pretrained model backbone required to support more advanced downstream clinical NLP tasks, particularly NER and structured information extraction.

The contribution of MS16 is to take this foundation a step further by integrating the domain-adapted models into deep learning-based NER pipelines for cardiology. Rather than focusing only on the ability of language models to represent clinical text, the milestone evaluates how these representations can be used to identify clinically meaningful mentions in unstructured EHR narratives and assign them to predefined semantic categories. The work therefore shifts the focus from language model adaptation to clinical concept recognition, while maintaining a direct methodological link with the resources, corpora and model improvements developed in previous WP3 activities.

In practical terms, the cardiology-adapted language models are used as contextual encoders that generate language- and domain-aware representations of clinical text across the project languages. These representations are then used by NER architectures to detect and classify spans of text corresponding to relevant clinical entities. The milestone focuses on a selected set of high-impact entity types aligned with the DataTools4Heart clinical use cases and downstream data structuring needs: diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications. These categories capture essential information for cardiovascular research and care and constitute a first semantic layer toward the structured representation of clinical documentation.

This work also follows the iterative strategy defined in WP3, where existing medical NER resources are adapted to cardiology content, multilingual semantically annotated corpora are generated and progressively refined, and model performance is improved through data enrichment, active learning strategies and clinician-in-the-loop validation. This iterative approach is particularly important in a multilingual European setting, where the availability, quality and domain coverage of clinical NLP resources differ substantially across languages. By combining domain-adapted language models with multilingual annotated datasets and expert validation, MS16 aims to produce NER systems that are both technically robust and clinically meaningful.

The outputs produced by these systems are designed to support the broader DataTools4Heart interoperability pipeline. Recognised entities are represented as structured NLP annotations compatible with the DT4H NLP-CDM/FHIR-oriented profile, including record-level metadata and annotation-level information such as concept class, character offsets, mention string, confidence score, NER component type and version, and contextual attributes such as negation. The structure also includes fields for terminology mapping and controlled vocabulary identifiers, preparing the recognised entities for subsequent normalization and semantic harmonization.

MS16 therefore provides the structured extraction component that bridges unstructured multilingual EHR text and the downstream DT4H data structuring pipeline. The milestone does not aim to complete the full concept normalization process; instead, it establishes the clinical concept recognition layer upon which future entity linking, terminology alignment and harmonization components can be built. By integrating multilingual cardiology-adapted language models into deep learning-based NER systems, MS16 constitutes a central step towards scalable, multilingual and interoperable clinical data extraction for European cardiology EHRs.

3 Methodology Overview

This section describes the overall methodological pipeline underlying the development of multilingual deep learning-based clinical NER systems within DataTools4Heart. The pipeline comprises three interdependent components: (1) the creation and progressive refinement of multilingual biomedical and cardiology corpora, (2) the clinical-domain adaptation of language models (Task 3.1), and (3) the design and training of NER systems (Task 3.4).

3.1 Multilingual Corpora

Large-scale multilingual corpora combining cardiology-specific texts, biomedical literature, and clinical notes were assembled for the continual pre-training of language models. To evaluate the quality of the resulting models, the Parallel CLInical Text (ParaCliTe) corpus of synthetic clinical narratives was used as the primary intrinsic benchmark. For NER training and evaluation, the project relies on the Cardiology Clinical Case Corpus (CardioCCC), produced progressively through iterative annotation rounds. This corpus covers the seven consortium languages and is described in detail in Section 4.

3.2 Language Model Adaptation

Existing transformer-based encoder models were adapted to the clinical domain through continual pre-training on the multilingual biomedical and cardiology corpora mentioned above. The resulting CardioBERTa¹ model family provides domain-aware contextual representations that serve as the backbone for downstream NER systems. The language model adaptation strategy, architectures, and evaluation are described in detail in Section 5.

¹ <https://huggingface.co/collections/DT4H/cardioberta-family>

3.3 Named Entity Recognition Systems

The NER systems target four clinically relevant entity types selected for their importance in cardiovascular care documentation: diseases, symptoms, procedures, and medications. NER is formulated as a multi-label token classification task using the Beginning–Inside–Outside (BIO) tagging scheme, with a classification head added on top of each transformer encoder. Once extracted, the recognised entities feed directly into the broader DataTools4Heart pipeline as structured inputs, enabling data interoperability and reusability across European institutions. The model architecture, training strategies, and fine-tuning procedures are described in Section 6.

3.4 Iterative Development Cycle

A defining characteristic of the methodology is its iterative approach to data creation and model development. Rather than relying on a static training corpus, the pipeline follows a progressive cycle in which dataset size increases across successive annotation rounds, annotation quality improves as trained models assist through pre-annotation, and model performance feeds back into the annotation workflow. The underlying principle is that improvements in data quality and language model representations directly enhance downstream entity recognition performance. This iterative refinement is described in detail in Section 6.2, and its quantitative impact is reported in Section 7.

Figure 2 illustrates the end-to-end pipeline from language model pre-training to NER system development. A base transformer architecture is first pre-trained on generic corpora to produce a general-domain language model (base BERT² model). This stage, performed externally, produces the publicly available checkpoints used as starting points. From these pre-trained checkpoints, two paths diverge: continual pre-training on biomedical and cardiology-specific corpora, yielding the domain-adapted CardioBERTa models, and direct fine-tuning on the annotated CardioCCC corpus, producing a base NER model. CardioBERTa is then also fine-tuned on CardioCCC to produce the CardioNER model. This dual-path design enables a controlled comparison of NER performance with and without domain adaptation, quantifying the contribution of cardiology-specific pre-training to downstream entity recognition (Section 7).

Figure 2: End-to-end pipeline from general-domain pre-training to cardiology NER system development.

² Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019, June). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies, volume 1 (long and short papers)* (pp. 4171-4186).

4 Multilingual Clinical Datasets

Various multilingual clinical datasets have been created in the context of DT4H. These datasets will be openly published and thus available. They represent a unique suite of multilingual resources for NLP in cardiology. They will facilitate the expansion of clinical NLP resources in minority languages, and benchmarking for clinical NLP/ AI solutions.

4.1 Cardiology Clinical Case Corpus (CardioCCC)

CardioCCC is a corpus of 508 cardiology clinical case reports annotated with diseases, symptoms and findings, clinical procedures and medications in the seven Consortium languages (Czech, Dutch, English, Italian, Romanian, Spanish, and Swedish). The dataset's texts were originally collected and annotated in Spanish and then translated and projected into the other six languages in order to obtain a comparable, multilingual dataset.

Given the challenges of working with real clinical records, including data protection constraints, institutional access barriers, and restrictions on cross-site data sharing, it was decided to create a dataset of clinical case reports. Clinical case reports are narrative documents published in clinical journals that describe specific patient encounters in a similar manner to real clinical records, including medical history, current problem, procedures, treatment, and follow-up. Since they are published in journals, they are already anonymized, avoiding the data protection barriers associated with real patient data. Their structural and content similarity to actual EHR narratives makes them a suitable basis for training baseline clinical NER systems that can later be adapted to real clinical records. To build CardioCCC, articles from open-access cardiology journals in Spanish were selected, crawled and pre-processed. Special attention was paid to clinical case reports related to heart failure in order to obtain a collection of documents closely aligned with the use cases of the project.

The annotation of the selected clinical case reports in Spanish was done by senior clinical annotators who had previously worked on other similar annotation tasks. They followed annotation criteria already established for previous corpora published in Spanish such as DisTEMIST³ for diseases or MedProcNER⁴ for clinical procedures. These corpora were published as part of shared tasks in international conferences, becoming benchmarks for the extraction of clinical concepts in Spanish. The decision to follow the same guidelines was twofold: on the one hand, using existing guidelines, already proven and validated, significantly sped up the annotation process, which otherwise would have had to go through an annotation definition and annotator training phase which would take up to months; on the other hand, by following the same criteria as other corpora, the new annotations generated for CardioCCC would be compatible with these other resources, potentially expanding the pool of documents usable for training and testing automatic extraction systems. To complement the latter point, the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) has worked on multiple corpora using the same guidelines, including the corpus of anonymized COVID-19 clinical records in Spanish and Catalan CARMEN-I⁵, reinforcing their validity and utility.

For CardioCCC, only some minor adjustments had to be made to account for cardiology-specific content that was not part of the original guidelines. A joint version of the annotation guidelines, covering the four

³ Miranda-Escalada, A., Gascó, L., Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., Estrada, D., Nentidis, A., ... & Krallinger, M. (2022). Overview of DisTEMIST at BioASQ: Automatic detection and normalization of diseases from clinical texts: results, methods, evaluation and multilingual resources. *CLEF (Working Notes)*, 3180, 179-203.

⁴ Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., Gasco, L., Nentidis, A., Krithara, A., Katsimpras, G., ... & Krallinger, M. (2023). Overview of MedProcNER Task on Medical Procedure Detection and Entity Linking at BioASQ 2023. In *CLEF (Working Notes)* (pp. 1-18).

⁵ Farre Maduell, E., Lima-Lopez, S., Frid, S. A., Conesa, A., Asensio, E., Lopez-Rueda, A., Arino, H., Calvo, E., Bertran, M. J., Marcos, M. A., Nofre Maiz, M., Tañá Velasco, L., Marti, A., Farreres, R., Pastor, X., Borrat Frigola, X., & Krallinger, M. (2024). CARMEN-I: A resource of anonymized electronic health records in Spanish and Catalan for training and testing NLP tools (version 1.0.1). *PhysioNet*. RRID:SCR_007345. <https://doi.org/10.13026/x7ed-9r91>

entity types used in this project as well as additional categories such as species and human mentions, was created in the context of the aforementioned CARMEN-I but also used for CardioCCC. These guidelines are available on Zenodo in both Spanish⁶ and English⁷. Importantly, the guidelines were originally generated in Spanish and manually translated into English by a professional clinical translator. In terms of content, the guidelines include an introduction explaining their purpose, origin and creation process, as well as some indications for the annotators. Then, a set of general rules is explained, as well as rules specific to each entity type divided into different types with descriptions and examples for each. The complete document, including references, is 54-pages-long in Spanish and 52-pages-long in English.

All in all, CardioCCC was annotated with four entity types: diseases, symptoms and findings, clinical procedures and medications. It was decided to focus on these semantic categories, and not others, since it was considered that they broadly covered most of the information described in the project’s clinical variables. Table 1 provides a description and some examples for all four labels.

Table 1: Description of the four semantic categories (labels) annotated in the CardioCCC corpus.

Label	Description	Examples
DISEASE	Clinical conditions that affect the normal functioning of the body and that have a certain extension in time.	“pericardial effusion”, “endomyocardial fibrosis”, “cardiogenic shock”, “pulmonary oedema”, “stroke with left hemiplegia”
SYMPTOM	This label covers three distinct clinical concepts: symptoms (understood as manifestations of clinical conditions that are often self-reported and may be subjective); signs (manifestations observed by health professionals); and findings (test results, such as laboratory tests and X-rays).	“eupneic at rest”, “murmurs”, “preserved left ventricular systolic function”, “anginal chest pain”, “narrow QRS”
PROCEDURE	Procedures are actions or interventions performed by health professionals in order to diagnose or treat diseases and health problems. Medication family names are included within this label. Administrative procedures (e.g. “discharge”) are not included.	“valve replacement surgery”, “transthoracic echocardiogram”, “catheterisation”, “cardiac auscultation”, “vasoactive drugs”
MEDICATION	Specific products, compounds or substances with a defined molecular composition and a therapeutic purpose.	“warfarin”, “heparin”, “noradrenaline”, “candesartan”, “furosemide”

Once the Spanish dataset was created, an annotation projection methodology was used to develop the same resource in the remaining six languages. Starting from the seed corpus in Spanish, the clinical case reports and annotations were translated into each of the six other project languages. Once the translations had been obtained, the resulting translated annotations were mapped onto the translated texts. The mapping was performed via a dictionary lookup using, for every document, only the annotations in each original annotated file as a way to avoid false positives.

⁶ Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., & Krallinger, M. (2023). CARMEN-I: Clinical Entities Annotation Guidelines in Spanish. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10171540>

⁷ Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., & Krallinger, M. (2024). CARMEN-I: Clinical Entities Annotation Guidelines in English. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14049620>

The automatic version resulting from this process was manually revised by clinicians from each clinical site. Using the side-by-side view of the BRAT⁸ annotation tool, clinicians saw the Spanish Gold Standard version on one side and the automatically generated translation on the other. Their task was to correct the translated version in their language to match the original as closely as possible. Figure 3 depicts an example of the annotation tool used by the clinicians. Despite not being fluent in Spanish, the task is relatively easy to perform thanks to the side-by-side view, which features numbered lines. The provided automatic suggestions generated by the automatic mapping, as well as being mindful of sentence structure and context, also aid in the task. To make sure the clinicians understood the task, a short training was imparted in various meetings with the clinicians in charge of each language. Additionally, annotation guidelines explaining the projection task, as well as some basic rules, were created and shared with the clinicians. These guidelines, named “Validation and Correction Guidelines for the Multilingual Annotation Projection of Gold Standard Corpora”, are publicly available on Zenodo⁹. Moreover, on top of the manual validation of the mentions themselves, clinicians were also asked to provide alternative suggestions for any annotated mentions whose translation was not correct or idiomatic. These suggestions were later used to create a second version of the dataset. In this version, the text of mentions with suggestions is replaced by the provided alternative, improving the overall quality of the automatic translations.

<p>1 Se presenta el caso de un paciente de 80 años con una DISEASE endocarditis sobre válvula protésica biológica, de etiología incierta que provocó un absceso sobre la válvula con dehiscencia del anillo. DISEASE</p> <p>2 El paciente no tenía alergias conocidas. DISEASE</p> <p>3 Era exfumador de 20 cig/día desde hacía más 20 años, y DISEASE consumidor de 2 copas de vino al día.</p> <p>4 Independiente para actividades básicas de la vida diaria.</p> <p>5 Hace 2 años acudió a urgencias de su centro hospitalario de referencia por disnea progresiva hasta hacerse de mínimos esfuerzos.</p> <p>6 El paciente en esta fecha tenía como antecedentes personales DISEASE glaucoma, hiperuricemia, DM II e hipercolesterolemia.</p> <p>7 En la ecocardiografía transtorácica (ETT) realizada durante el</p>	<p>1 We present the case of an 80-year-old patient with SUG_ENFERMEDAD endocarditis on a biological prosthetic valve, of uncertain aetiology, which caused an abscess on the valve with dehiscence of the annulus.</p> <p>2 The patient had no known SUG_ENFERMEDAD allergies.</p> <p>3 He had been an SUG_ENFERMEDAD ex-smoker of 20 cigarettes/day for more than 20 years, and consumed 2 glasses of wine per day.</p> <p>4 Independent for basic activities of daily living.</p> <p>5 Two years ago he went to the emergency department of his reference hospital for progressive dyspnoea to the point of minimal effort.</p> <p>6 At that time, the patient had a personal history of SUG_ENFERMEDAD glaucoma, SUG_ENFERMEDAD SUG_ENFERMEDAD hyperuricaemia, DM II and hypercholesterolaemia.</p> <p>7 Transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) performed during admission</p>
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Figure 3: Example of the BRAT side-by-side annotation interface used for the annotation projection step. On the left side, there is a Gold Standard document with annotated diseases in Spanish, while on the right side there is an uncorrected document in English with automatic suggestions.

Using an annotation projection methodology to create the multilingual corpus not only significantly speeds up the annotation process, making the annotator training process easier and removing the need for language-specific guidelines, but also results in a dataset that is comparable across languages. Since the dataset contains the same documents, albeit in different languages, annotated with the same criteria, the performance comparison across languages is fairer. It also gives a more controlled output in every language than using external resources, each annotated with a different set of criteria and a different number of documents and document types. Finally, it is important to note that the annotation process took place in multiple batches and that a quality control was performed as a final step. This is developed in Section 4.5.

⁸ Stenetorp, P., Pyysalo, S., Topic, G., Ohta, T., Ananiadou, S., & Tsujii, J. (2012). brat: a Web-based Tool for NLP-Assisted Text Annotation. *Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*.

⁹ Lima-López, S., Gasco, L., Farré-Maduell, E., & Krallinger, M. (2024). Validation and Correction Guidelines for the Multilingual Annotation Projection of Gold Standard Corpora. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13151040>

Table 2 shows the total number of annotations in the final version of the CardioCCC dataset. Each language contains over 55,000 mentions distributed over the four different labels, with diseases and symptoms usually being the most common types. Across all seven languages of the project, the dataset amounts to over 400,000 annotations, making it a significant contribution for biomedical NLP in general, and for cardiology-focused information extraction, in particular. For some of the languages with fewer available resources, such as Czech and Romanian, this contribution is even more valuable. Finally, Figure 4 shows a parallel example of the corpus in all languages.

Table 2: Full statistics of the complete CardioCCC dataset (508 clinical case reports) across language and labels, as well as the total sum of annotations.

Language	Label				TOTAL
	DISEASE	MEDICATION	PROCEDURE	SYMPTOM	
Spanish	18,232	4,227	17,073	19,983	59,515
Czech	17,788	4,290	16,477	18,729	57,284
English	17,097	4,231	15,708	18,694	55,730
Dutch	17,646	4,317	16,195	18,590	56,748
Italian	18,175	4,385	16,521	19,467	58,548
Swedish	17,588	4,241	16,131	18,489	56,449
Romanian	17,546	4,239	16,379	18,068	56,232
TOTAL	124,072	29,930	114,484	132,020	400,506

4.2 Parallel CLInical Text (ParaCliTe)

Parallel CLInical Text (ParaCliTe) is a multilingual parallel corpus of synthetic cardiovascular clinical texts developed as an output of Task 3.2. This dataset, comprising approximately 350,000 words evenly distributed across seven languages, was created by selecting a total of 94 clinical reports from CliTe (see corpus description in Section 4.3) and then professionally translating these texts into six additional languages. Available in both document-aligned and segment-aligned views, ParaCliTe is enriched with detailed metadata such as clinical annotations for symptoms, heart disorders, and comorbidities, as well as contextual clarifications of domain-specific terminology. Designed primarily for research in NLP and medical AI, it supports tasks like machine translation, automated medical coding, and cross-lingual information retrieval, all while ensuring data privacy through the use of fictional patient data.

The selection of the 94 documents aimed at balancing fictional patient sex in both the number of whole reports and their total word count. The selection also reflects the type of document that the local clinicians considered more relevant. In this respect, some languages included larger hospital discharge reports (Czech, Romanian, Spanish), while some others contained shorter in- and outpatient notes (Dutch, Swedish, English). The selection resulted in a corpus that contains a minimum of 7,000 words per language and a good sex balance (52% of documents and 24,717 words refer to female patients, while 48% of documents and 26,670 words to male patients). After this selection process, professional medical translators were recruited for each of the 42 language pairs, with at least two translators assigned per direction to ensure quality control. The selection of candidate translators prioritized previous experience in medical translation. Translators received concise guidelines outlining the project’s aim. They were instructed to treat the simulated reports as actual clinical texts and to preserve style, abbreviations and

structure while ensuring medical and terminological accuracy. Translators were instructed to log unclear acronyms, context issues, and questions which were submitted to clinicians for clarification in a final review round.

Spanish: pocos minutos, presenta bloqueo auriculoventricular completo con rachas de asistolia prolongada e inestabilidad hemodinámica, por lo que se procede a intubación orotraqueal y conexión a ventilación mecánica. Precisa de noradrenalina para mantener la tensión arterial.

English: minutes later, he presented complete atrioventricular block with bouts of prolonged asystole and haemodynamic instability, so orotracheal intubation and connection to mechanical ventilation was performed. He required noradrenaline to maintain blood pressure.

Czech: několik minut později se objevila kompletní atrioventrikulární blokáda se záchvaty prolongované asystolie a hemodynamickou nestabilitou, proto byla provedena orotracheální intubace a napojení na mechanickou ventilaci. K udržení krevního tlaku potřeboval noradrenalin.

Italian: minuti dopo, ha presentato un blocco atrioventricolare completo con attacchi di asistolia prolungata e instabilità emodinamica, per cui è stata eseguita l'intubazione orotracheale e il collegamento alla ventilazione meccanica. Ha richiesto noradrenalina per mantenere la pressione arteriosa.

Dutch: paar minuten later vertoonde hij een compleet atrioventriculair blok met vlagen van langdurige asystole en hemodynamische instabiliteit, dus werd orotracheale intubatie en aansluiting op mechanische beatdeming uitgevoerd. Hij had noradrenaline nodig om de bloeddruk op peil te houden.

Romanian: va minute mai târziu, a prezentat bloc atrioventricular complet cu crize de asistolie prelungită și instabilitate hemodinamică, astfel că s-a efectuat intubarea orotraheală și conectarea la ventilație mecanică. A avut nevoie de noradrenalină pentru a menține tensiunea arterială.

Swedish: A minuter senare uppvisade han fullständigt atrioventrikulärt block med anfall av långvarig asystoli och hemodynamisk instabilitet, så orotrakeal intubation och anslutning till mekanisk ventilation utfördes. Han behövde noradrenalin för att upprätthålla blodtrycket.

Figure 4: Selected text fragment of a clinical case report from the CardioCCC corpus that shows the same annotated example in all seven languages. At the top, the original fragment annotated in Spanish, followed vertically by its equivalent version created via annotation projection and manual validation in English, Czech, Italian, Dutch, Romanian and Swedish. Notably, the fragment shows all four possible label entity types: diseases (brown annotations), symptoms (red annotations), procedures (yellow annotations) and medications (purple annotations).

The translation process involved multiple stages and was supported by MateCat¹⁰, an open-source computer-assisted translation platform that enables real-time editing, alignment, and terminology consistency checks. The process started with a first-pass translation by a professional translator, which was followed by a quality review by an independent second translator. A final feedback loop between translators and clinicians was performed to clarify domain-specific terms and abbreviations. For some language directions, such as Romanian to Czech, qualified direct translators were not available, requiring translations to be completed via English as a pivot language: this process involved the use of a previously translated English version of a given non-English text, which was used as starting point for the following translation to the target language. Quality assurance combined technical and expert review components, while MateCat's intrinsic functions provided validation of segmentation, tag consistency, and completeness. Human revision addressed linguistic adequacy, terminological precision, and stylistic coherence.

After the generation of all translations, each text was further categorized at complete report level by the members of the coordinating team with relevant expertise to ensure consistency and add clinically-relevant metadata. During this annotation process, the following metadata were added: presence of relevant comorbidities and risk factors (smoking status, reduced mobility, obesity or overweight, diabetes, hypertension, kidney disease and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease), presence of symptoms at presentation (shortness of breath, oedema, chest pain, palpitation and NYHA class), presence of arrhythmias (including its categorization into atrial fibrillation or others), and presence of implanted devices (pacemakers, artificial heart valves, coronary stents, and left ventricle pump devices).

The final corpus consists of artificial reports featuring fictional patients aligned with their six corresponding translations. The metadata that accompany the corpus are organized to allow for seamless linkage to each corresponding source document at document level. A finer segmentation of the text was provided with the MateCat segmentation tool, resulting in the segmentation of each report into sentences, which were matched to its six translations. All the documents were normalized into a plain text (.txt) format.

Applying the methodology described above resulted in a dataset of 94 unique adult patient cases, each available in all seven languages, yielding 658 documents in total. This “one case, seven reports” design is the direct output of the manual translation and quality-control workflow; every source report is translated into the remaining six languages, preserving the underlying clinical scenario while allowing language-specific realizations typical of local reporting conventions. The released corpus is therefore parallel at the case/ report level across all languages, enabling controlled multilingual comparisons where the only intended variable is the language of the narrative. Each case is released with structured metadata, enabling stratified evaluation by language, condition, encounter type, or demographic information, without requiring post hoc inference from the text. ParaCliTe also includes a clarifications file that records ambiguous or underspecified expressions for which translators requested clarification from the clinicians during the translation workflow, together with the resolved interpretation (key information to build a cross-lingual cardiology glossary grounded in real translation-time uncertainties).

The final corpus contains approximately 51,400 words, with a deliberate tight range of approximately 7,000 word counts per language (Figure 5). This balance is an explicit consequence of the corpus design and curation steps described in Section 2, aimed at avoiding downstream bias arising from large-volume differences between languages. The stable word counts across languages indicate that the translation process preserved comparable content volume across language versions, which is important for fair evaluation in multilingual settings. The dataset comprises 91 adult fictional patients with a mean age of

¹⁰ Federico, M., Bertoldi, N., Cettolo, M., Negri, M., Turchi, M., Trombetti, M., ... & Germann, U. (2014, August). The matecat tool. In Proceedings of COLING 2014, the 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations (pp. 129-132).

58±18 years (Figure 2, Table 1) and an age distribution skewed toward older groups, which aligns with the typical epidemiology of cardiovascular disease and reflects clinical plausibility. The corpus is sex balanced, both in terms of number of documents per sex (49 documents for female patients and 45 for males), and in terms of number of words (24,717 words are associated with female cases and 26,670 words with male cases, 48.1% and 51.9% of total words, respectively).

Figure 5: Visual representation of the main characteristics of the ParaCliTe corpus.

4.3 CliTe Corpus

The CliTe dataset emerged as a multilingual collection of 697 artificially generated clinical reports. These reports were written by experts following the *Guiding Principles for Multilingual Generation of Artificial Case Reports*, which will be published as part of the forthcoming deliverables (more details in Section 4.4). The reports originate from seven different hospitals in 7 different countries and languages, illustrating the linguistic diversity found in medical texts across Europe. Table 3 shows the involved hospitals, together with their corresponding language and the number of reports produced by each.

Table 3: Distribution of artificial clinical reports by hospital, city, and language.

Hospital	City	Language	Number of Artificial case reports
Saint Anne's University Hospital	Brno	Czech	100
University Medical Centre	Utrecht	Dutch	100
University College London Hospital	London	English	100
Fondazione Policlinico A. Gemelli	Rome	Italian	96
Bucharest Emergency Clinical Hospital	Bucharest	Romanian	101
Vall d'Hebron University Hospital	Barcelona	Spanish	100
Karolinska University Hospital	Stockholm	Swedish	100

Please note that Saint Anne's has produced a total of 246 artificial case reports, of which only 100 are included in CliTe for language balance purposes. Also, because these cases are entirely fictional and contain no real patient data, no ethical approval was necessary.

The process began with a small set of artificial cardiology cases, each drafted by one or more clinical experts and reviewed by NLP specialists. Once validated, clinicians were invited to expand the dataset, encouraged to create a rich and varied collection of reports. The length of these documents varies widely, reflecting both local clinical traditions and personal preferences. Some clinicians leaned toward longer, detailed narratives, like hospital discharge summaries, while others preferred shorter, concise formats, such as inpatient, outpatient notes.

To make the CliTe dataset as useful as possible beyond its initial creation, every report was paired with structured metadata. Clinicians were asked to label each case with: (1) an identifier; (2) original language; (3) the fictional patient's sex and age; (4) the primary cardiac diagnosis; (5) the type of document (outpatient or inpatient notes, discharge summary, or referral letter).

Following the guidelines, we aimed to produce a balanced set, particularly in terms of sex. Table 4 shows the distribution of reports by patient gender and report type, as well as patient age statistics (mean and range).

Table 4: Data distribution of the CliTe corpus.

CliTe	Number	Percentage
Patient's sex		
Female	353	51%
Male	344	49%
Age		
Average Female	62	NA
Average Male	60	NA
Average Total	61	NA
Range Female	20-110	NA
Range Male	19-94	NA
Range Total	19-110	NA
Report type		
Outpatient notes	341	49%
Discharge summary	264	40%
Inpatient notes	88	10.50%
Referral letters	4	0.50%

Regarding diagnoses, a physician manually grouped them into broader categories. This approach revealed that the two most common diagnoses in the corpus, namely, ischemic heart disease and heart failure, align with the leading causes of cardiovascular-related consultations and deaths. However, the dataset also captures a wide range of other cardiovascular conditions commonly seen in clinical practice, such as valve disease and syncope.

It is important to note that these are the primary diagnoses assigned by cardiologists. The medical records may also include additional cardiovascular conditions. For example, a patient with a primary diagnosis of heart failure might also have hypertension and an old myocardial infarction. Less frequent diagnoses are grouped under the category "Other," which includes conditions like postpartum cardiomyopathy, myocarditis, and palpitations. Please see Figure 6 for the distribution of heart conditions in CliTe.

CLiTe: Distribution per main heart condition

Figure 6: Distribution of heart conditions in CLiTe.

4.4 Artificial Clinical Cases Guidelines

Artificial clinical records, i.e., manually written by clinical experts mimicking real texts in EHRs, are becoming essential for medical NLP and AI development. Unlike real patient data, restricted due to privacy concerns, these records provide researchers with a realistic dataset for training and validating AI models.

For this project, we created custom made guidelines to define the backbone of artificial clinical reports sets. To start with, two seed reports were developed by a cardiologist in Spanish, translated into seven target languages and distributed among the authors of the corpus. These initial reports served as blueprints, demonstrating how artificial records could adapt to different linguistic characteristics.

Next, the cardiologists from the seven hospitals – University Medical Centre Utrecht (Dutch), Fondazione Policlinico A. Gemelli (Italian), St. Anne's University Hospital Brno (Czech), University College London Hospital (English), Vall d'Hebron University Hospital (Spanish), Karolinska University Hospital (Swedish) and Bucharest Emergency Clinical Hospital (Romanian) – created their own samples in each language. Their goal was twofold: to replicate their hospital's documentation style as closely as possible while ensuring the records avoided biases and represented the diversity of patients with regard to age, sex and health condition. Feedback from the authors was integrated into the guidelines, refining the framework to address challenges and improve clarity. By prioritizing transparency and rigor, this approach ensures that AI models trained on artificial data are practical, trustworthy, unbiased solutions ready for real-world application.

4.5 Iterative Data Improvement

The data annotation process was managed as an iterative and sequential process, in which clinicians were provided with batches of documents to work with. At first, only a few documents were provided to train the clinicians as annotators and make sure they understood the task. Then, bigger batches were shared for them to work on. The annotations of the dataset were also split into two groups: on the one hand, diseases

and procedures, and, on the other hand, symptoms and medications. This was done in order not to overload clinicians with too many annotations at once, which could have resulted in unwanted errors.

A batch-based annotation process also made it possible to reduce the manual workload, since each new batch incorporated suggestions based on the work done in the previous batch. Finished batches were also shared with the technical side so that they could start working and experimenting with intermediate trained models.

Once the annotation was done, some post-processing of the annotations was done to ensure their quality. This process was done semi-automatically, with specific types of errors being located using rules and then checked manually. Some of the aspects processed included: annotations that start or finish with punctuation, annotations that included incomplete words or annotations that had more than one label assigned to them. In addition, some documents whose number of annotations greatly differed with the Spanish reference were also manually revised and corrected.

Finally, it is worth noting that, in spite of the significant number of annotations and resources created for the project, there is still some room for improvement. The number of resources available in Spanish, mainly due to the effort of the scientific community around this language in the last few years, is still higher than for most other languages, which could result in a disparity between the performance of the trained models. This is being addressed with the creation of new comparable datasets using the same annotation projection methodology using as a reference some of the Spanish resources mentioned earlier in this section, such as DisTEMIST¹¹ and MedProcNER¹². Next, despite the advantages offered by the annotation projection methodology, the resulting datasets are based on machine-translated data, which could have some unseen effects. To address this possible issue, datasets that use clinical case reports originally written in each of the project's languages are also being created. Overall, the addition of these datasets to what's already covered in CardioCCC will result in more robust NER models across all languages.

5 Multilingual Clinical Language Models

The DataTools4Heart project developed and evaluated seven clinical language models adapted to the cardiology domain across the consortium languages: English, Spanish, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Swedish, and Czech. The objective of this work was to improve the representation of specialized cardiovascular terminology and clinical narrative structure in downstream NLP applications such as NER, information extraction, and clinical document understanding. The work builds upon the activities and results reported in MS5. For more details, we refer to the document *MS5_DataTools4Heart_BSC_30052025*.

5.1 Model Architectures and Configurations

The adopted strategy relied on continual pretraining of existing transformer-based encoder models using multilingual cardiology and biomedical corpora derived from EHRs, synthetic discharge summaries, biomedical literature, and translated medical resources. Depending on the language and availability of suitable checkpoints, either monolingual biomedical models or multilingual general-purpose models were selected as initialization backbones (see Table 5).

¹¹ Miranda-Escalada, A., Gascó, L., Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., Estrada, D., Nentidis, A., ... & Krallinger, M. (2022). Overview of DisTEMIST at BioASQ: Automatic detection and normalization of diseases from clinical texts: results, methods, evaluation and multilingual resources. *CLEF (Working Notes)*, 3180, 179-203.

¹² Lima-López, S., Farré-Maduell, E., Gasco, L., Nentidis, A., Krithara, A., Katsimpras, G., ... & Krallinger, M. (2023). Overview of MedProcNER Task on Medical Procedure Detection and Entity Linking at BioASQ 2023. In *CLEF (Working Notes)* (pp. 1-18).

Table 5: Base models overview.

Language	Base-model name	Architecture	Pre-training task	Model size (# trainable parameters)	Corpus size (# words)
Romanian	FacebookAI/xlm-roberta-base ¹³	XLM-RoBERTa	MLM	270M	4.4B
Swedish	KB/bert-base-swedish-cased ¹⁴	BERT	MLM, NSP	110M	2.6B
Spanish	PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-biomedical-clinical-es ¹⁵	BERT	MLM, NSP	125M	3.8B
Italian	IVN-RIN/bioBIT ¹⁶	BERT	MLM, NSP	109M	4.8B
English	allenai/biomed_roberta_base ¹⁷	RoBERTa	MLM	125M	800M
Dutch	CLTL/MedRoBERTa.nl ¹⁸	RoBERTa	MLM	125M	5.4B
Czech	ufal/Robeczech-base ¹⁹	RoBERTa	MLM	125M	2.9B

The central architecture is BERT, where BERT/RoBERTa/XLM-RoBERTa in Table 5, refer to the same architecture but with different pre-training objectives. For the continuous pre-training we used monolingual datasets. The pre-training objective for all methods was *masked-language modelling (MLM)* – see Figure 7; here we randomly mask a token with a masking probability of between 10-50% (where larger model sizes benefit from larger masking probabilities).

5.2 Multilingual Corpora

The multilingual training corpora combined cardiology-specific texts, biomedical literature, and clinical notes. Due to the uneven availability of clinical resources between languages, tailored acquisition and preprocessing strategies were necessary. In particular, lower-resource languages such as Romanian, Czech, and Swedish required additional machine-translated biomedical content and synthetic clinical material to achieve sufficient corpus scale for stable continual pretraining (see Figure 8).

¹³ Conneau, A., Khandelwal, K., Goyal, N., Chaudhary, V., Wenzek, G., Guzmán, F., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2020, July). Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale. In *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics* (pp. 8440-8451).

¹⁴ Malmsten, M., Börjeson, L., & Haffenden, C. (2020). Playing with Words at the National Library of Sweden--Making a Swedish BERT. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.01658*.

¹⁵ Biomedical and Clinical Language Models for Spanish: On the Benefits of Domain-Specific Pretraining in a Mid-Resource Scenario
¹⁶ Buonocore, T. M., Crema, C., Redolfi, A., Bellazzi, R., & Parimbelli, E. (2023). Localizing in-domain adaptation of transformer-based biomedical language models. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 144, 104431.

¹⁷ Gururangan, S., Marasović, A., Swayamdipta, S., Lo, K., Beltagy, I., Downey, D., & Smith, N. A. (2020, July). Don't stop pretraining: Adapt language models to domains and tasks. In *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics* (pp. 8342-8360).

¹⁸ Verkijk, S., & Vossen, P. (2025). Creating, anonymizing and evaluating the first medical language model pre-trained on Dutch Electronic Health Records: MedRoBERTa. nl. *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 167, 103148.

¹⁹ Straka, M., Náplava, J., Straková, J., & Samuel, D. (2021, August). RobeCzech: Czech RoBERTa, a monolingual contextualized language representation model. In *International conference on text, speech, and dialogue* (pp. 197-209). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Figure 7: Existing pre-training objectives.

Figure 8: Data collection acquisition.

The multilingual training corpora combined cardiology-specific texts, biomedical literature, and clinical notes. Due to the uneven availability of clinical resources between languages, tailored acquisition and preprocessing strategies were necessary. In particular, lower-resource languages such as Romanian, Czech, and Swedish required additional machine-translated biomedical content and synthetic clinical material to achieve sufficient corpus scale for stable continual pretraining.

Data preprocessing included normalization of encoding artifacts, exact and fuzzy deduplication, domain-specific filtering using cardiology-related terminology, and corpus balancing. For biomedical article selection, regular-expression filtering and MeSH-based retrieval strategies were employed to isolate cardiovascular content from larger medical repositories.

5.3 Domain Adaptation Strategies

The domain adaptation strategy followed a continual pretraining paradigm, where existing transformer language models were further trained on in-domain cardiology and biomedical corpora using masked language modeling objectives. This approach enables models to retain their broad linguistic knowledge while adapting their internal representations to the vocabulary, syntax, and semantic patterns characteristic of clinical and cardiovascular documentation.

A major consideration in model selection was the trade-off between multilingual coverage and domain specialization. For languages where biomedical checkpoints were already available (e.g., English, Spanish, Dutch, and Italian), these models provided a strong initialization point because they had already been exposed to biomedical terminology during earlier pretraining stages. In contrast, languages lacking specialized checkpoints, such as Romanian, relied on multilingual general-domain models like XLM-RoBERTa²⁰.

The continual pretraining process was organized around shard-based sequential training or via an in-buffer randomized streamed loader over a shuffled list of partial corpora. For the former, large corpora were partitioned into manageable subsets, and each model was iteratively fine-tuned over these shards for multiple epochs. For the latter we collected the corpora into one parquet file, which was randomized and split into many smaller parquet files, these smaller files could then be randomly ingested with in-buffer shuffling. This strategy reduced computational bottlenecks while ensuring progressive exposure to large quantities of clinical data. The training setup employed distributed GPU execution, AdamW optimization, linear warm-up schedules, and sliding-window tokenization to handle long clinical documents. The use of many pre-randomized partial corpus files allowed for low-memory data loading and robust restarts.

The continual pretraining workflow was executed primarily on the MareNostrum 5 supercomputing infrastructure using distributed PyTorch training across multiple NVIDIA H100 GPUs, and in the Google TPU cloud for research. Training was performed sequentially over corpus shards to accommodate large-scale multilingual datasets while maintaining reproducibility and manageable runtime constraints. Hyperparameters were largely standardized across languages, including sliding-window chunking with 512-token context windows and masked language modeling objectives.

5.4 Evaluation Metrics

Several evaluation metrics were used to quantify the effectiveness of continual pretraining and domain adaptation.

²⁰ Conneau, A., Khandelwal, K., Goyal, N., Chaudhary, V., Wenzek, G., Guzmán, F., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2020, July). Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale. In *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics* (pp. 8440-8451).

5.4.1 Pseudo-perplexity

Pseudo-perplexity was used as the principal intrinsic evaluation metric for masked language models. Since transformer encoder architectures such as BERT²¹ and RoBERTa²² do not compute autoregressive perplexity directly, pseudo-perplexity estimates model confidence by masking tokens and measuring the likelihood of recovering them from context. Lower pseudo-perplexity values indicate stronger familiarity with domain-specific language.

Evaluation was conducted on the multilingual ParaCliTe corpus, which contains synthetic cardiovascular clinical narratives aligned across the seven languages. Documents were processed using sliding windows of 512 tokens with overlapping strides to preserve contextual continuity. After continual pretraining, substantial reductions in pseudo-perplexity were observed for English, Spanish, Czech, and Romanian, demonstrating successful adaptation to cardiology terminology and narrative style.

5.4.2 Named Entity Recognition

To evaluate downstream clinical utility, the models were assessed on multilingual NER tasks using the CardioCCC corpus. This dataset contains clinically annotated entities such as diseases, medications, procedures, and symptoms across the seven consortium languages. Entity annotations were converted into BIO tagging format for transformer-based sequence labeling.

Performance was measured at both token and word levels using precision, recall, and macro-averaged F1 score. Token-level evaluation assessed subword prediction quality, while word-level evaluation evaluated the reconstruction of complete entity spans after subword aggregation.

Results showed that continual pretraining generally preserved or modestly improved NER performance. English and Swedish achieved measurable token-level gains, while Spanish and Dutch demonstrated notable improvements at the word level. In languages where perplexity gains were limited, downstream NER performance still remained stable, suggesting that domain adaptation benefited entity extraction even when intrinsic language modeling improvements were smaller.

5.5 Multilingual Considerations

A major challenge in multilingual clinical NLP is the uneven distribution of available biomedical and clinical data across languages. While English and Spanish benefit from comparatively rich biomedical ecosystems and existing domain-specific checkpoints, lower-resource languages such as Romanian, Czech, and Swedish lack large-scale publicly available clinical corpora. To address this imbalance, the project combined several complementary strategies, including machine-translated biomedical abstracts, synthetic clinical text generation, and multilingual transfer learning.

Cross-lingual transfer played an important role, particularly for Romanian, where no specialized biomedical checkpoint was available. In this case, XLM-RoBERTa provided multilingual representations learned from over one hundred languages, enabling adaptation to clinical Romanian despite limited native-domain resources. This demonstrates the practical value of multilingual pretrained models for low-resource medical NLP scenarios.

The project also highlighted the trade-offs between monolingual and multilingual approaches. Monolingual biomedical models generally achieved stronger specialization because their vocabularies and internal

²¹ Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019, June). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies, volume 1 (long and short papers)* (pp. 4171-4186).

²² Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2019). Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*.

representations were optimized for domain-specific terminology in a single language. However, multilingual models offered broader scalability and better support for transfer learning in languages with limited training material.

Results further suggested that the effectiveness of domain adaptation depends strongly on the starting checkpoint. Languages initialized from already-specialized biomedical models often exhibited smaller perplexity improvements because much of the clinical knowledge was already encoded in the base model. Conversely, multilingual or general-domain models showed larger gains after continual pretraining, indicating greater benefit from targeted cardiology adaptation.

Collectively, these findings suggest that multilingual clinical NLP requires flexible adaptation strategies that balance domain specificity, language coverage, and computational feasibility. The resulting multilingual CardioBERTa family constitutes a reusable foundation for multilingual clinical NLP within the DataTools4Heart ecosystem, particularly for cardiology-oriented information extraction and structured clinical data interoperability.

6 Named Entity Recognition Systems for Cardiology

The NER systems developed within Task 3.4 build directly upon the cardiology-adapted language models described in Section 5. Domain-specific continual pre-training of transformer-based encoders on cardiology and biomedical corpora substantially improved the models' representation of clinical language, as measured by pseudo-perplexity reductions on the ParaCliTe corpus. The resulting CardioBERTa models, enriched with cardiology-specific terminology, abbreviations, and syntactic patterns, provide high-quality contextual representations that improve NER systems' ability to distinguish clinical entity boundaries and classify entity types. Nevertheless, as the evaluation in Section 7 demonstrates, training strategy, data coverage, and annotation quality are equally influential factors in overall system performance.

This section describes how these domain-adapted language models are integrated into scalable NER systems capable of extracting structured clinical information from cardiology reports across all seven consortium languages, as well as the iterative development methodology and active learning strategies employed to progressively refine model performance.

6.1 Model Architecture and Training Strategy

The NER systems were designed to automatically identify and classify mentions of four clinically relevant entities (diseases, symptoms, procedures, and medications) from unstructured clinical text in seven European languages: Czech, Dutch, English, Italian, Romanian, Spanish, and Swedish.

6.1.1 Transformer-based Encoders

The NER systems leverage three types of pre-trained transformer-based encoder architectures as their backbone:

- i. **Language-specific BERT models** fine-tuned for general-domain NER, covering six of the seven consortium languages (Dutch is covered under iii), as follows:
 - a. **Czech:** xlm-ner-slavic²³;
 - b. **English:** bert-base-NER²⁴;

²³ Ivačić, N., Tran, T. H. H., Koloski, B., Pollak, S., & Purver, M. (2023, May). Analysis of transfer learning for named entity recognition in south-Slavic languages. In *Proceedings of the 9th Workshop on Slavic Natural Language Processing 2023 (SlavicNLP 2023)* (pp. 106-112).

²⁴ Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019, June). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies, volume 1 (long and short papers)* (pp. 4171-4186).

- c. **Italian**: bert-italian-finetuned-ner²⁵;
 - d. **Romanian**: bert-base-romanian-ner²⁶;
 - e. **Spanish**: bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner²⁷;
 - f. **Swedish**: bert-base-swedish-cased-ner²⁸.
- ii. **CardioBERTa models**²⁹: The seven cardiology-adapted language models developed under Task 3.1 and described in Section 5, which underwent continual pre-training on biomedical and cardiology-specific corpora. These models capture domain-specific knowledge that enhances downstream NER performance.
 - iii. **Multilingual models**:
 - a. **bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl**³⁰: used in monolingual settings for all languages it supports (English, Spanish, Italian), and serving as the sole model for Dutch, where no language-specific alternative exists.
 - b. **XL-M-RoBERTa-large**³¹: employed in both monolingual and multilingual fine-tuning settings. This model leverages cross-lingual transfer to benefit low-resource languages where domain-specific pre-training data is limited.

6.1.2 Task Formulation

The NER task is formulated as a multi-label token classification problem using the standard BIO tagging scheme. In this format, each token is assigned one of three positional tags per entity type: B (beginning of an entity), I (inside an entity), or O (outside any entity). This scheme is widely adopted due to its explicit boundary clarity, seamless alignment with sequence labeling architectures, and interoperability across NLP tools and systems.

A token classification head is added on top of the transformer encoder, consisting of a linear layer that maps each token's contextual representation to the BIO label space. The model outputs per-token probability distributions, from which entity labels are predicted. The full NER pipeline involves two stages, as shown in Figure 9:

- i. **Token-level prediction**: The encoder processes input text and the classification head assigns BIO label probabilities to each sub-word token.
- ii. **Span estimation and post-processing**: At inference time, token-level predictions are aggregated into entity spans through a combination of heuristics, including probability thresholds for accepting token classes, resolution of inconsistent tag sequences (e.g., converting orphan I-tags to B-tags), and special character handling. The output is converted from BIO format back to character-offset annotations in BRAT format for evaluation.

²⁵ Stefan Schweter. (2020). Italian BERT and ELECTRA models (1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4263142>

²⁶ Dumitrescu, S. D., & Avram, A. M. (2020, May). Introducing ronec-the romanian named entity corpus. In *Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference* (pp. 4436-4443).

²⁷ <https://huggingface.co/mrm8488/bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner>

²⁸ <https://huggingface.co/KBLab/bert-base-swedish-cased-ner>

²⁹ <https://huggingface.co/collections/DT4H/cardioberta-family>

³⁰ <https://huggingface.co/Davlan/bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl>

³¹ Conneau, A., Khandelwal, K., Goyal, N., Chaudhary, V., Wenzek, G., Guzmán, F., ... & Stoyanov, V. (2020, July). Unsupervised cross-lingual representation learning at scale. In *Proceedings of the 58th annual meeting of the association for computational linguistics* (pp. 8440-8451).

Figure 9: Multilabel span prediction.

6.1.3 Fine-tuning Strategies

The pre-trained encoders described in 6.1.1 are fine-tuned on the annotated CardioCCC corpus for clinical entity recognition. Two training strategies were developed, differing in input segmentation, evaluation protocol, and training procedure:

Method 1 – Sentence-level token classification

This approach splits clinical case reports into individual sentences, ensuring a sequence length ≤ 256 tokens, and trains models on a fixed 80/20 split. Each sentence is further segmented into word-level tokens while preserving character offsets with respect to the original report. The word-level tokens are encoded in BIO format using the available BRAT annotations. Models were fine-tuned on an NVIDIA RTX A5000 GPU (24 GB) for 10 epochs, with a batch size of 8, a learning rate of 9×10^{-6} , and a maximum sequence length of 256. This approach was employed for the initial NER system development.

Method 2 – Paragraph-level chunking with 10-fold cross-validation and checkpoint merging

Instead of sentence-level splitting, documents are segmented at the paragraph level using a cascade strategy: texts are successively divided into paragraphs, lines, and sentences, retaining at each step only segments that fit within the 256-token context window. This preserves broader context within each input sequence. Tokenization and BIO encoding follow the same process as in Method 1. Models were trained using 10-fold cross-validation (10 epochs per fold, batch size of 16, learning rate of 9×10^{-6}), maximising training data utilisation. The resulting ten-fold checkpoints are averaged into a single merged model, ensuring that the final model has effectively been trained on the entire dataset.

The impact of these strategies is quantified in Section 7.

6.2 Iterative Development and Active Learning Strategy

The NER pipeline was developed in two phases: an initial model development phase followed by an iterative annotation–training loop that progressively expanded the training data over successive rounds.

6.2.1 Initial Model Development

General-domain transformer models were first fine-tuned on the CardioCCC corpus to establish initial NER performance baselines across all seven languages. The domain-adapted CardioBERTa models were then used as backbones and fine-tuned on the same corpus, measuring the impact of cardiology specific continual pre-training on NER performance.

6.2.2 Iterative Annotation and Retraining Cycle

Once baseline performance was established, an iterative annotation–training cycle was initiated to progressively expand and refine the training data and improve model performance. Each iteration follows these steps:

- a. **Pre-annotation and model-assisted labelling:** Trained NER models were used to generate pre-annotations on new unlabeled clinical texts. These pre-annotations reduce the annotation effort required from clinical experts by providing an initial set of entities for correction rather than annotating from scratch.
- b. **Expert validation and correction:** Clinical experts review and correct the model-generated pre-annotations. This clinician-in-the-loop approach ensures high annotation quality while maintaining efficiency.
- c. **Model retraining:** Corrected annotations are incorporated into the training set, and models are retrained with the expanded and improved data, yielding better-performing models for the next iteration.
- d. **Quality assessment and refinement:** Each iteration includes a systematic evaluation of model outputs and identification of common error patterns (e.g., boundary detection issues, entity type confusion), informing adjustments to training configuration and post-processing heuristics in subsequent rounds.

This iterative cycle follows the "tag a little, learn a little" active learning principle in which data annotation and model training alternate so that each iteration benefits from the improvements of the previous one. Rather than annotating a large corpus at once, the annotation process is distributed across successive rounds, each expanding the training set incrementally with expert-validated data. Improvements in annotation quality and model performance achieved in one language further inform the development in other languages through annotation projection and multilingual model fine-tuning. The impact of this progressive data scaling on NER performance quantified in Section 7.

7 Evaluation and Results

7.1 Evaluation Setup and Metrics

A comprehensive evaluation framework was established to assess both the language models developed under Task 3.1 and the NER systems developed under Task 3.4. The evaluation employs standardized metrics to enable consistent comparison across languages and model configurations.

7.1.1 Language Model Evaluation

For evaluating the quality of domain-adapted language models, pseudo-perplexity is used as the primary intrinsic metric. Pseudo-perplexity measures how well a masked language model predicts masked tokens in domain-specific text: lower values indicate a tighter fit to the target domain and greater model confidence

when encountering cardiology-specific vocabulary. Pseudo-perplexity is computed on the ParaCliTe multilingual corpus, which provides parallel clinical text across all seven consortium languages, enabling direct cross-lingual comparison of language model quality.

7.1.2 NER Evaluation

The NER systems are evaluated using standard information extraction metrics: precision, recall, and F1-score. These metrics are computed along two independent dimensions.

The first dimension is the **matching criterion**, which determines when a predicted entity counts as correct:

- a. **Strict evaluation:** a prediction is considered correct only if both the entity type and the exact character offsets match the gold-standard annotation. This is the most demanding evaluation setting, penalizing any boundary detection errors.
- b. **Relaxed (character-overlap) evaluation:** a prediction is considered correct if the entity type is correct and there is any character-level overlap between the predicted and gold-standard spans. This setting captures cases where the model correctly identifies the entity type and approximate location but fails to match exact boundaries.

The second dimension is the **aggregation method**, which determines how scores are combined across entity types:

- a. **Micro-averaging:** Metrics are computed globally across all entity instances, giving more weight to frequent entity types.
- b. **Macro-averaging:** Metrics are computed per entity type and then averaged, giving equal weight to each type regardless of frequency.

Both dimensions are reported in combination to provide a comprehensive view of performance, particularly in the presence of class imbalance across entity types.

7.1.3 Evaluation Benchmark

All NER systems described in this milestone are evaluated on the CardioCCC corpus, which covers the seven languages and four entity types. The evaluation protocol differs between methods: Method 1 uses a fixed 80/20 train/test split, while Method 2 uses 10-fold cross-validation for training and a separate holdout set for evaluation, with results averaged across folds.

7.1.4 Evaluation Tools

A dedicated leaderboard was developed to evaluate and benchmark all NER models (Figure 10). The leaderboard employs both strict and relaxed metrics based on precision, recall, and F1-score using macro and micro averaging, providing a comprehensive assessment of model performance across languages and entity types.

Choose Dataset
cardioccc_it_med

Leaderboard

** 🏆 🏆 🏆 The default metric is: Micro strict **

Submission Name/ HF Revision	Model Link	Person Name	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Date	Actions
2025-05-28_09-48-43-fa4cf1b	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	Manuela Voinea	0.90	0.87	0.88	2025-07-09 10:52:57	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-07-09_13-23-04-b80b5cb0	bioBIT	Manuela Voinea	0.90	0.88	0.89	2025-07-09 10:51:29	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-05-28_09-58-42-9285c6d0	bert-italian-finetuned-ner.it_IT_MED	Manuela Voinea	0.89	0.88	0.89	2025-05-28 09:06:26	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-05-28_09-53-25-62fb1193	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl.it_IT_MED	Manuela Voinea	0.89	0.87	0.88	2025-05-28 09:06:47	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-05-28_09-56-35-2be26590	bert-italian-finetuned-ner.it_IT_MED	Manuela Voinea	0.88	0.88	0.88	2025-05-28 08:59:33	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-05-19_08-26-01-dcbf0fb3	CardioBERTa.it_IT_MED	Wesam	0.89	0.91	0.90	2025-05-19 11:22:57	🗑️ 📄 📌
2025-05-07_21-27-06-e5272867	CardioBERTa.it_IT_MED	Wesam	0.86	0.90	0.88	2025-05-07 22:17:54	🗑️ 📄 📌

Submit Your Model Prediction

Upload TSV

Drag and drop file here
Limit 200MB per file • TSV

Browse files

Figure 10: Leaderboard for evaluating and benchmarking NER models using strict and relaxed precision, recall, and F1-score metrics.

Results are publicly accessible through an interactive demo, illustrated in Figure 11, available on the HuggingFace platform at the following link: <https://huggingface.co/spaces/DT4H-IE/DT4H-NER-Demo>.

Spaces DT4H-IE / DT4H-NER-Demo like 3 Running Logs

App Files Settings

Multi-task NER

Select a language, enter text, and run all 4 models (MED, DIS, SYMP, PROC).

Also accessible via API

Select Language: en

Text Input: and symmetrically distributed. In this context, blood cultures, urine cultures and serology were negative and there was no PCR detection of cytomegalovirus, pneumocystis jirovecii (in bronchoalveolar lavage and respiratory viruses), negative smear microscopy, PCR for tuberculosis in bronchoalveolar lavage and bronchoaspirate and negative mycobacterial culture. Galactomannan for aspergillus in bronchoalveolar lavage negative. Negative PCR for Leishmania in bone marrow.

Threshold: 0.5

56 Predicted Entities (All Models Combined)

History

Male, 45 years old. No drug allergies DISEASE, No arterial hypertension DISEASE, no diabetes mellitus DISEASE, no dyslipidaemia DISEASE, No known heart disease DISEASE or bronchopathy DISEASE. Advanced chronic kidney disease on haemodialysis programme PROCEDURE, secondary to autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease. Renal transplant PROCEDURE in May 2018 with acute rejection on the 10th day with good subsequent response. Proximal deep vein thrombosis at the level of superficial femoral, popliteal vein and deep and twin branches of left lower limb in November 2018 in current treatment with acenocoumarol MEDICATION. Pyelonephritis of the renal graft DISEASE in March 2019 with good response to antibiotic treatment PROCEDURE. Current treatment: prednisone MEDICATION 20 mg/24 hours, tacrolimus MEDICATION 4 mg/24 hours, omeprazole MEDICATION 20 mg/24 hours, enoxaparin MEDICATION 60 mg/24 hours and furosemide MEDICATION 40 mg/24 hours.

Present illness

He was admitted from the nephrology department for clinical manifestations of fever, predominantly nocturnal SYMPTOM, up to 38.3°C, of 2 weeks of evolution, together with exertional dyspnoea SYMPTOM, NYHA III, orthopnoea SYMPTOM, oedematization of the lower limbs SYMPTOM and cough SYMPTOM with whitish expectoration SYMPTOM. He had been admitted 2 months previously for the same reason with partial improvement and without identification of the aetiology, but the symptoms recurred after discontinuation of antibiotic therapy PROCEDURE. No micturition symptoms SYMPTOM, no alterations in bowel habits SYMPTOM.

Figure 11: Overview of the interactive Hugging Face demo allowing real-time exploration of NER models.

7.2 Language Model Evaluation Results

The domain adaptation of language models was evaluated by comparing pseudo-perplexity scores before and after cardiology-specific continual pre-training (see Section 5 for base model details and pre-training corpora). Table 6 summarizes the results across all seven languages.

Table 6: Pseudo-perplexity comparison between base and cardiology-adapted language models, evaluated on the ParaCliTe corpus. Lower values indicate better domain adaptation.

Language	Base Model	Pre-trained Model	Variation
English	12.01	6.87	-0.4280
Spanish	26.33	2.25	-0.9145
Swedish	4.79	5.55	0.1594
Czech	10.25	5.27	-0.4859
Italian	5.28	6.80	0.2879
Romanian	67.43	11.94	-0.8229
Dutch	3.98	6.7	0.68

Notable pseudo-perplexity reductions were observed for Spanish (-91.45%), Romanian (-82.3%), Czech (-48.6%), and English (-42.8%). These results indicate substantially improved model confidence on domain-specific vocabulary, particularly for languages whose base models were general-domain or multilingual and lacked cardiology-specific content.

In contrast, Swedish (+15.9%), Italian (+28.8%), and Dutch (+68.0%) exhibited perplexity increases after domain adaptation. This divergence can be attributed to the fact that the base checkpoints for these languages already contained considerable biomedical or clinical content (e.g., MedRoBERTa.nl for Dutch was pre-trained on hospital notes), meaning that the domain-specific pre-training data distribution may partially conflict with the existing model knowledge rather than adding new information.

Critically, as will be shown in Section 7.3, this pseudo-perplexity increase does not correlate with degraded NER performance. Languages with increased perplexity maintained or improved their NER scores, demonstrating that the relationship between intrinsic language model quality and downstream task performance is not strictly linear.

7.3 NER Performance

The NER systems were evaluated on the CardioCCC dataset to assess the impact of domain specific continual pre-training on entity recognition.

7.3.1 Method 1 (Per-entity Performance Analysis on CardioCCC)

The evaluation of NER performance per entity type reveals important patterns across clinical concepts.

MEDICATION

Medication recognition (Table 7) achieves the highest performance of all entity types, with strict F1 ranging from 0.88 to 0.92 across languages. CardioBERTa matches or slightly improves the base models in all cases, with the largest gains in Swedish (+0.03), Italian (+0.02) and Dutch (+0.02). The small gap between strict and relaxed evaluation (~2–3 points) indicates precise boundary detection for this entity type.

Table 7: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for medication recognition. Precision, recall, and F1 are reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	xlm-ner-slavic	0.88 (0.91)	0.88 (0.91)	0.88 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.89 (0.92)	0.89 (0.92)	0.89 (0.92)
Dutch	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.88 (0.89)	0.86 (0.87)	0.9 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.9 (0.92)	0.9 (0.91)	0.91 (0.92)
English	bert-base-NER	0.91 (0.93)	0.9 (0.92)	0.93 (0.94)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.92 (0.93)	0.92 (0.94)	0.91 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.92 (0.93)	0.94 (0.95)	0.9 (0.91)
Italian	bert-italian-finetuned-ner	0.89 (0.9)	0.88 (0.89)	0.89 (0.91)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.88 (0.9)	0.87 (0.88)	0.9 (0.91)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.9 (0.92)	0.91 (0.93)	0.89 (0.9)
Romanian	bert-base-romanian-ner	0.9 (0.92)	0.93 (0.95)	0.87 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.91 (0.94)	0.94 (0.96)	0.89 (0.91)
Spanish	bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner	0.92 (0.93)	0.91 (0.92)	0.93 (0.94)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.92 (0.93)	0.91 (0.92)	0.93 (0.95)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.92 (0.95)	0.92 (0.96)	0.91 (0.95)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased-ner	0.88 (0.9)	0.89 (0.9)	0.88 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.91 (0.92)	0.91 (0.92)	0.9 (0.92)

DISEASE

Disease recognition (Table 8) is substantially harder than identifying medication mentions, with strict F1 ranging from 0.57 (Italian) to 0.78 (Spanish). CardioBERTa improves Czech (+0.02), English (+0.02), and Dutch (+0.01) but slightly hurts Spanish (-0.04) and Italian (-0.02). The strict-relaxed gap is notably larger for diseases (~15–18 points), suggesting that boundary detection is more challenging for multi-word disease mentions.

Table 8: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for disease recognition. Precision, recall, and F1 are reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	xlm-ner-slavic	0.66 (0.84)	0.65 (0.83)	0.68 (0.85)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.68 (0.86)	0.66 (0.84)	0.69 (0.88)
Dutch	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.68 (0.85)	0.67 (0.84)	0.69 (0.87)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.69 (0.87)	0.68 (0.86)	0.7 (0.87)
English	bert-base-NER	0.67 (0.85)	0.67 (0.85)	0.66 (0.84)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.67 (0.84)	0.64 (0.8)	0.7 (0.88)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.69 (0.85)	0.66 (0.82)	0.72 (0.89)
Italian	bert-italian-finetuned-ner	0.58 (0.71)	0.66 (0.81)	0.52 (0.63)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.59 (0.71)	0.66 (0.8)	0.53 (0.64)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.57 (0.71)	0.65 (0.81)	0.51 (0.63)
Romanian	bert-base-romanian-ner	0.7 (0.86)	0.69 (0.86)	0.7 (0.87)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.68 (0.86)	0.68 (0.86)	0.68 (0.87)
Spanish	bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner	0.78 (0.9)	0.78 (0.91)	0.77 (0.9)

	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.78 (0.9)	0.78 (0.91)	0.77 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.74 (0.89)	0.76 (0.9)	0.73 (0.87)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased-ner	0.69 (0.86)	0.68 (0.85)	0.69 (0.87)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.69 (0.87)	0.68 (0.86)	0.7 (0.88)

PROCEDURE

Procedure recognition (Table 9) achieves 0.67–0.82 strict F1 across languages, with Spanish reaching the highest scores (0.8–0.82) and the remaining languages clustered between 0.67 and 0.74. CardioBERTa provides small improvements in most languages (+0.01 to +0.02), with only Romanian showing a slight decline (−0.01).

Table 9: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for procedure recognition. Precision, recall, and F1 are reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	xlm-ner-slavic	0.69 (0.83)	0.66 (0.78)	0.74 (0.88)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.71 (0.84)	0.67 (0.78)	0.76 (0.89)
Dutch	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.71 (0.84)	0.67 (0.8)	0.76 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.72 (0.86)	0.69 (0.82)	0.75 (0.9)
English	bert-base-NER	0.71 (0.83)	0.65 (0.76)	0.77 (0.91)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.71 (0.85)	0.68 (0.82)	0.74 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.73 (0.86)	0.7 (0.82)	0.77 (0.91)
Italian	bert-italian-finetuned-ner	0.67 (0.77)	0.74 (0.84)	0.62 (0.71)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.67 (0.76)	0.74 (0.84)	0.62 (0.7)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.67 (0.77)	0.74 (0.85)	0.61 (0.7)
Romanian	bert-base-romanian-ner	0.74 (0.86)	0.71 (0.83)	0.77 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.73 (0.86)	0.7 (0.82)	0.76 (0.89)
Spanish	bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner	0.81 (0.91)	0.82 (0.92)	0.8 (0.9)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.8 (0.91)	0.81 (0.92)	0.8 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.82 (0.92)	0.83 (0.93)	0.81 (0.9)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased-ner	0.72 (0.86)	0.71 (0.84)	0.74 (0.87)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.73 (0.86)	0.7 (0.82)	0.77 (0.9)

SYMPTOM

Symptom recognition (Table 10) achieves 0.55–0.76 strict F1 across languages. Spanish performs best (0.76), followed by English (0.69) and Swedish (0.68), while Italian shows the lowest scores (0.55–0.56). CardioBERTa effects are minimal and inconsistent: slight improvements in Czech and English are counterbalanced by neutral or negative results in other languages.

Table 10: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for symptom recognition. Precision, recall, and F1 are reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	xlm-ner-slavic	0.63 (0.81)	0.62 (0.79)	0.65 (0.83)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.65 (0.82)	0.6 (0.75)	0.71 (0.89)
Dutch	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.66 (0.81)	0.62 (0.77)	0.7 (0.86)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.65 (0.82)	0.63 (0.79)	0.68 (0.86)
English	bert-base-NER	0.68 (0.82)	0.66 (0.79)	0.71 (0.85)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.69 (0.83)	0.67 (0.8)	0.72 (0.85)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.69 (0.84)	0.69 (0.83)	0.7 (0.85)
Italian	bert-italian-finetuned-ner	0.56 (0.66)	0.69 (0.81)	0.47 (0.56)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.56 (0.66)	0.68 (0.8)	0.48 (0.57)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.55 (0.65)	0.68 (0.81)	0.46 (0.55)
Romanian	bert-base-romanian-ner	0.61 (0.78)	0.63 (0.8)	0.59 (0.76)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.62 (0.78)	0.64 (0.81)	0.6 (0.76)
Spanish	bert-spanish-cased-finetuned-ner	0.76 (0.88)	0.76 (0.88)	0.75 (0.87)
	bert-base-multilingual-cased-ner-hrl	0.74 (0.87)	0.76 (0.89)	0.72 (0.84)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.76 (0.88)	0.76 (0.89)	0.75 (0.87)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased-ner	0.68 (0.82)	0.65 (0.79)	0.71 (0.86)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.67 (0.83)	0.65 (0.8)	0.7 (0.86)

Under Method 1, Spanish consistently achieves the highest scores, which is expected given that CardioCCC was originally authored in this language. CardioBERTa provides the most reliable gains for medications and procedures, while its impact on diseases and symptoms is smaller and language-dependent.

7.3.2 Method 2 (Multilabel Performance Analysis on CardioCCC)

All results were obtained under a 10-fold cross-validation setup with full model update, aggregated over the four entity types, and averaged across folds. Tables 11 and 12 present span-level performance under strict matching, where an entity is counted as correct only when both its boundaries and predicted type match the reference exactly, with macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 reported across the four entity types.

XLM-RoBERTa-large achieves 0.73–0.77 macro F1 and 0.69–0.74 micro F1, substantially above base models and CardioBERTa. Micro scores are consistently lower than macro, indicating that the entity types contributing more instances to the evaluation tend to have lower individual F1 scores. The consistent gap between strict and relaxed metrics across all models shows that most errors stem from imprecise span boundary identification rather than incorrect entity type prediction. XLM-RoBERTa-large achieves the highest macro F1 in six of seven languages, demonstrating that a single multilingual checkpoint, fine-tuned jointly on all languages, can match or surpass dedicated monolingual models, confirming cross-lingual training as an effective strategy for multilingual clinical NER.

A notable outlier is Czech CardioBERTa, which drops to 0.17 macro F1 due to a severe recall collapse (0.12) while precision remains high (0.75), suggesting the model becomes overly conservative in the multilabel setting, missing the vast majority of entities while remaining precise on the few it does predict. As shown in the per-entity evaluation (Section 7.3.3), Czech CardioBERTa matches or improves over base models across all four entity types when trained separately, confirming that this degradation is specific to the multi-entity interaction rather than a general quality issue of the adapted model.

Table 11: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC, using a multilabel, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are aggregated over the four entity types and averaged across folds, with macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 reported.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.39 (0.49)	0.28 (0.35)	0.75 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.17 (0.24)	0.12 (0.16)	0.75 (0.97)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.86)	0.73 (0.86)	0.74 (0.87)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.68 (0.83)	0.68 (0.83)	0.68 (0.82)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.68 (0.83)	0.67 (0.81)	0.7 (0.85)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.86)	0.72 (0.85)	0.74 (0.87)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.68 (0.82)	0.68 (0.82)	0.68 (0.82)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.69 (0.82)	0.69 (0.82)	0.69 (0.83)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.74 (0.85)	0.74 (0.85)	0.74 (0.86)
Italian	bioBIT	0.68 (0.84)	0.65 (0.81)	0.66 (0.86)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.68 (0.85)	0.66 (0.81)	0.67 (0.87)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.86)	0.72 (0.85)	0.74 (0.87)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.68 (0.83)	0.69 (0.84)	0.68 (0.82)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.7 (0.85)	0.71 (0.86)	0.68 (0.83)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.86)	0.72 (0.85)	0.74 (0.87)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.63 (0.77)	0.57 (0.69)	0.73 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.63 (0.79)	0.57 (0.7)	0.73 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.77 (0.89)	0.77 (0.89)	0.77 (0.89)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.7 (0.83)	0.7 (0.84)	0.69 (0.83)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.73 (0.87)	0.74 (0.88)	0.72 (0.86)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.86)	0.73 (0.86)	0.73 (0.86)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.75 (0.88)	0.74 (0.88)	0.75 (0.89)

Table 12: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC, using a multilabel, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are aggregated over the four entity types and averaged across folds, with micro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 reported.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.4 (0.5)	0.27 (0.35)	0.74 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.2 (0.28)	0.11 (0.16)	0.67 (0.93)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.85)	0.7 (0.85)	0.7 (0.86)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.63 (0.81)	0.64 (0.82)	0.63 (0.8)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.65 (0.82)	0.63 (0.8)	0.67 (0.84)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.85)	0.69 (0.84)	0.71 (0.86)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.64 (0.8)	0.65 (0.8)	0.64 (0.79)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.65 (0.8)	0.65 (0.8)	0.65 (0.81)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.71 (0.84)	0.71 (0.84)	0.71 (0.84)
Italian	bioBIT	0.63 (0.82)	0.61 (0.79)	0.66 (0.86)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.64 (0.83)	0.62 (0.80)	0.67 (0.87)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.69 (0.85)	0.69 (0.84)	0.7 (0.86)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.64 (0.81)	0.65 (0.82)	0.64 (0.8)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.66 (0.82)	0.67 (0.85)	0.65 (0.81)

	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.85)	0.69 (0.84)	0.7 (0.86)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.63 (0.79)	0.56 (0.69)	0.72 (0.89)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.63 (0.79)	0.57 (0.7)	0.73 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.74 (0.88)	0.74 (0.88)	0.75 (0.89)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.66 (0.82)	0.66 (0.82)	0.65 (0.81)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.69 (0.85)	0.7 (0.86)	0.68 (0.84)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.85)	0.7 (0.85)	0.7 (0.86)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.71 (0.88)	0.71 (0.87)	0.72 (0.88)

7.3.3 Method 2 (Multiclass Performance Analysis on CardioCCC)

MEDICATION

Medication recognition (Table 13) remains the easiest entity type also under Method 2, with strict F1 ranging from 0.84 to 0.92. Spanish and Swedish achieve the highest scores (0.91–0.92). All three model families achieve comparable performance, with differences of at most 4 F1 points within any language, suggesting that base monolingual models already capture this entity type effectively, leaving little room for improvement through either domain adaptation or multilingual scale.

Table 13: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for medication recognition, using a multiclass, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are averaged across folds, with precision, recall, and F1 reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.85 (0.9)	0.85 (0.89)	0.86 (0.91)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.84 (0.91)	0.84 (0.91)	0.84 (0.91)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.87 (0.92)	0.86 (0.91)	0.88 (0.92)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.88 (0.9)	0.87 (0.88)	0.9 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.86 (0.9)	0.85 (0.89)	0.87 (0.91)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.87 (0.91)	0.86 (0.89)	0.88 (0.92)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.85 (0.91)	0.84 (0.9)	0.86 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.86 (0.91)	0.85 (0.9)	0.86 (0.92)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.89 (0.92)	0.9 (0.93)	0.87 (0.91)
Italian	bioBIT	0.87 (0.91)	0.83 (0.87)	0.92 (0.96)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.88 (0.92)	0.84 (0.88)	0.92 (0.97)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.86 (0.9)	0.87 (0.91)	0.85 (0.88)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.86 (0.91)	0.86 (0.9)	0.87 (0.91)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.88 (0.92)	0.89 (0.92)	0.89 (0.92)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.89 (0.92)	0.88 (0.91)	0.89 (0.93)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.91 (0.94)	0.9 (0.94)	0.91 (0.95)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.92 (0.95)	0.92 (0.96)	0.91 (0.95)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.9 (0.92)	0.91 (0.93)	0.89 (0.91)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.88 (0.91)	0.9 (0.93)	0.87 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.91 (0.92)	0.93 (0.95)	0.88 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.87 (0.91)	0.88 (0.92)	0.86 (0.9)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.9 (0.92)	0.9 (0.92)	0.89 (0.92)

DISEASE

Disease recognition (Table 14) is substantially harder, with strict F1 ranging from 0.62 to 0.75. XLM-RoBERTa-large dominates across all languages, outperforming base models by 3–9 points, with the largest gains in English (+9) and Dutch (+8). CardioBERTa matches or improves over base models in all languages (0 to +4 points), with the largest gains in Swedish (+4), Czech (+3), and Dutch (+3), though the improvement is consistently smaller than that provided by XLM-RoBERTa-large. The strict–relaxed gap is notably larger for diseases (13–17 points) than for medications, confirming that disease mentions present greater detection challenges.

Table 14: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for disease recognition, using a multiclass, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are averaged across folds, with precision, recall, and F1 reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.66 (0.85)	0.67 (0.86)	0.65 (0.83)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.69 (0.86)	0.71 (0.89)	0.67 (0.83)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.72 (0.87)	0.73 (0.88)	0.71 (0.86)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.63 (0.85)	0.61 (0.82)	0.64 (0.85)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.66 (0.86)	0.64 (0.83)	0.68 (0.89)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.71 (0.88)	0.72 (0.88)	0.71 (0.87)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.62 (0.79)	0.62 (0.79)	0.63 (0.8)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.62 (0.79)	0.62 (0.79)	0.62 (0.79)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.71 (0.84)	0.7 (0.82)	0.72 (0.85)
Italian	bioBIT	0.63 (0.83)	0.62 (0.81)	0.65 (0.85)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.64 (0.83)	0.61 (0.80)	0.67 (0.87)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.87)	0.7 (0.87)	0.71 (0.88)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.67 (0.85)	0.69 (0.88)	0.65 (0.82)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.69 (0.87)	0.71 (0.89)	0.67 (0.85)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.72 (0.89)	0.72 (0.88)	0.72 (0.88)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.72 (0.89)	0.72 (0.88)	0.73 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.73 (0.89)	0.75 (0.92)	0.72 (0.88)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.75 (0.9)	0.77 (0.92)	0.74 (0.89)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.65 (0.84)	0.66 (0.85)	0.64 (0.83)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.69 (0.87)	0.7 (0.89)	0.68 (0.86)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.71 (0.88)	0.72 (0.89)	0.71 (0.87)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.72 (0.89)	0.73 (0.9)	0.72 (0.89)

PROCEDURE

Procedure recognition (Table 15) spans 0.59–0.82 strict F1, with Spanish achieving the highest scores (0.82) and Italian the lowest (0.59). XLM-RoBERTa-large outperforms base models by 3–13 points across all languages. CardioBERTa provides modest improvements in Czech (+2) and Swedish (+3) but slightly hurts Italian (–1) and Spanish (–2), suggesting that domain adaptation interacts unevenly with language-specific procedure terminology.

Table 15: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for procedure recognition, using a multiclass, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are averaged across folds, with precision, recall, and F1 reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.73 (0.85)	0.72 (0.83)	0.76 (0.88)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.75 (0.86)	0.73 (0.84)	0.77 (0.88)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.76 (0.88)	0.75 (0.86)	0.78 (0.89)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.67 (0.82)	0.62 (0.76)	0.72 (0.88)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.68 (0.82)	0.62 (0.75)	0.74 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.74 (0.88)	0.72 (0.85)	0.76 (0.9)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.68 (0.81)	0.67 (0.8)	0.69 (0.82)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.69 (0.82)	0.68 (0.81)	0.71 (0.84)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.75 (0.85)	0.74 (0.84)	0.76 (0.86)
Italian	bioBIT	0.60 (0.82)	0.55 (0.75)	0.65 (0.9)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.59 (0.81)	0.54 (0.74)	0.66 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.73 (0.87)	0.71 (0.85)	0.75 (0.89)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.72 (0.85)	0.71 (0.84)	0.73 (0.87)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.73 (0.87)	0.73 (0.86)	0.73 (0.87)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.75 (0.87)	0.74 (0.86)	0.77 (0.89)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.79 (0.9)	0.77 (0.88)	0.81 (0.92)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.77 (0.89)	0.77 (0.89)	0.78 (0.9)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.82 (0.91)	0.82 (0.91)	0.82 (0.91)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.7 (0.85)	0.69 (0.83)	0.73 (0.88)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.73 (0.87)	0.73 (0.87)	0.73 (0.88)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.75 (0.88)	0.73 (0.87)	0.76 (0.9)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.76 (0.89)	0.75 (0.88)	0.78 (0.91)

SYMPTOM

Symptom is the hardest entity type (Table 16), with strict F1 ranging from 0.57 to 0.74. XLM-RoBERTa-large performs best in all languages, with gains of 3–13 points over base models. The largest improvements were achieved in English (+13) and Swedish (+12). CardioBERTa improves at most +3 points over base models and is slightly negative in Spanish (−1), indicating that domain adaptation alone provides limited benefit for symptom recognition. Model size and multilingual pre-training appear to be the decisive factors for this entity type.

Table 16: Span-level NER performance on CardioCCC for symptom recognition, using a multiclass, 10-fold cross-validation setup with full-model fine-tuning. Metrics are averaged across folds, with precision, recall, and F1 reported under both strict (exact boundary) and relaxed (overlapping boundary) matching.

Language	Model	F1 strict (relaxed)	Recall strict (relaxed)	Precision strict (relaxed)
Czech	robeczech-base	0.61 (0.79)	0.61 (0.79)	0.61 (0.79)
	CardioBERTa.cz	0.62 (0.79)	0.64 (0.82)	0.6 (0.76)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.67 (0.82)	0.69 (0.84)	0.66 (0.81)
Dutch	RobBERT2023-base	0.62 (0.77)	0.63 (0.81)	0.6 (0.77)
	CardioBERTa.nl	0.65 (0.8)	0.64 (0.79)	0.65 (0.81)

	xlm-roberta-large	0.69 (0.83)	0.7 (0.84)	0.67 (0.82)
English	biomed_roberta_base	0.57 (0.77)	0.60 (0.8)	0.55 (0.74)
	CardioBERTa.en	0.57 (0.77)	0.58 (0.78)	0.56 (0.76)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.7 (0.83)	0.71 (0.85)	0.68 (0.82)
Italian	bioBIT	0.60 (0.78)	0.57 (0.73)	0.64 (0.83)
	CardioBERTa.it	0.61 (0.79)	0.59 (0.74)	0.65 (0.84)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.67 (0.83)	0.68 (0.85)	0.66 (0.82)
Romanian	xlm-roberta-base	0.6 (0.75)	0.59 (0.75)	0.6 (0.76)
	CardioBERTa.ro	0.62 (0.77)	0.63 (0.79)	0.61 (0.76)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.63 (0.78)	0.63 (0.78)	0.64 (0.79)
Spanish	biomedical-clinical-es	0.68 (0.84)	0.69 (0.84)	0.68 (0.84)
	CardioBERTa.es	0.67 (0.82)	0.68 (0.85)	0.66 (0.83)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.74 (0.87)	0.75 (0.89)	0.72 (0.85)
Swedish	bert-base-swedish-cased	0.57 (0.78)	0.56 (0.76)	0.58 (0.8)
	CardioBERTa.sv	0.6 (0.81)	0.59 (0.79)	0.62 (0.82)
	xlm-roberta-large	0.69 (0.83)	0.7 (0.85)	0.68 (0.82)
Multilingual	xlm-roberta-large	0.69 (0.86)	0.7 (0.88)	0.68 (0.85)

The per-entity evaluation under Method 2 confirms the difficulty hierarchy established by Method 1 and demonstrates that XLM-RoBERTa-large provides the largest gains over base models across all languages and entity types, reinforcing its viability as a single multilingual deployment solution. CardioBERTa's performance in the single-entity setting is also more consistent than in the multilabel evaluation, with no severe degradations observed for any language.

7.3.4 Clinical Validation of NER Outputs

In addition to the quantitative evaluation reported in the previous sections, MS16 includes a clinical validation step designed to assess the practical quality, usefulness and limitations of the NER outputs from the perspective of clinical experts. This evaluation complements benchmark-based metrics with clinician judgement, which is essential for understanding whether the extracted entities are suitable for downstream use in real-world hospital environments.

The validation focused on a direct comparison between two types of systems. The first was a baseline extractor based on rules, dictionaries and the resources available at the beginning of the project. This baseline represents the type of entity extraction that could be achieved before the development of the DataTools4Heart multilingual transformer-based resources. The second was the Transformers-based NER system developed within MS16, trained using the annotated corpora and multilingual resources generated during the project. This comparison was designed to assess not only whether the neural models improve automatic entity recognition, but also whether clinicians perceive their outputs as more accurate, more useful and closer to practical deployment.

The clinical validation was conducted through a structured qualitative questionnaire completed by clinicians after inspecting the outputs generated by both systems. The questionnaire covered general system performance, entity-specific output quality, perceived usefulness, observed error types and free-text feedback. The evaluation focused on the four semantic categories targeted by the MS16 NER systems:

diseases, symptoms, procedures and medications. The questionnaires used in this validation will be made openly available through Zenodo³².

At this stage of the project, clinical evaluations were collected across five project languages: Spanish, Dutch, Czech, Swedish and Romanian. As shown in Figure 12, the current validation provides multilingual clinical feedback rather than evidence restricted to a single language or clinical documentation context. This is particularly relevant for DataTools4Heart, as the project aims to develop clinical NLP systems that can operate across heterogeneous European hospital settings, languages and reporting practices.

Figure 12: Distribution of clinical evaluations by language for the MS16 systems.

Building on this multilingual validation setup, the comparison between systems shows a clear and consistent improvement of the Transformers-based approach over the baseline across all evaluated categories. As shown in Figure 13, the baseline system obtained low mean clinical ratings across the complete output and all entity types, ranging from 16% for procedures to 26% for medications. In contrast, the Transformers-based system achieved substantially higher ratings in every category: 72% for the complete output, 66% for diseases, 64% for symptoms, 76% for procedures and 84% for medications. This corresponds to absolute improvements of +54 percentage points for the overall output, +44 points for diseases, +46 points for symptoms, +60 points for procedures and +58 points for medications.

³² <https://zenodo.org/records/20394666>

Figure 13: Comparative clinical evaluation of baseline and Transformers-based NER systems by entity type.

These improvements are important because they show that the systems developed within MS16 go substantially beyond the extraction approaches available before the project. The gain is not limited to a single entity type but is observed across the full set of clinically relevant categories targeted by the milestone. The strongest results were obtained for medications and procedures, two entity types with direct relevance for cardiology documentation, treatment characterisation and downstream data structuring. Medication extraction reached the highest clinical rating, suggesting that the system is already able to provide clinically meaningful outputs for one of the most structured and actionable entity categories. The strong improvement observed for procedure recognition is also relevant for the future transformation of clinical narratives into structured data aligned with hospital workflows and interoperability standards.

Moreover, the perceived usefulness of the systems reinforces this interpretation from a deployment-oriented perspective. Figure 14 shows a marked contrast between the baseline and the Transformers-based system in terms of potential usefulness for hospital implementation. For the baseline system, 80% of responses rated the automatic extraction as having only a limited degree of usefulness, while 20% considered it useful. In contrast, all responses for the Transformers-based system were positive: 60% of clinicians rated it as useful and 40% as very useful. No evaluator rated the Transformers-based system as having limited usefulness or as not useful. This result suggests that the improvement is not only measurable in terms of output quality, but also clinically meaningful for future integration into hospital-based NLP workflows.

Figure 14: Comparative assessment of the perceived usefulness of automatic clinical entity extraction for hospital implementation.

The qualitative feedback provided by evaluators helps explain both the strengths of the Transformers-based system and the remaining barriers to full deployment. Clinicians reported that the system detects a broader range of clinically relevant entities and produces more informative annotations than the baseline, confirming the added value of the resources and models developed during the project. At the same time, the evaluation identified several limitations that will guide the next refinement cycle. The main error patterns were related to semantic disambiguation, entity boundary precision and contextual interpretation. In particular, evaluators observed confusion between related entity types, especially symptoms and diseases; partial or over-extended spans; missed entities; and cases where negated or context-dependent mentions were still extracted as positive clinical entities.

These error patterns are consistent with the entity-level ratings shown in Figure 13. Medication and procedure extraction received the highest ratings, reflecting the more stable terminology and clearer mention boundaries typically associated with these categories. By contrast, diseases and symptoms obtained lower, although still substantially improved, ratings. This is expected given that these categories are more semantically variable, more dependent on context and more prone to overlap in clinical narratives. The clinical feedback therefore does not contradict the quantitative results; rather, it provides a more precise explanation of where the system is already robust and where targeted improvements are still required.

Taken together, the clinical validation demonstrates that the MS16 Transformers-based systems provide a substantial improvement over the initial baseline and are moving towards practical usability in clinical environments. The results show strong clinical acceptance, with all evaluators considering automatic entity extraction with the Transformers-based system useful or very useful. At the same time, the validation highlights the specific refinements required before full deployment, including improved handling of negation, better discrimination between closely related entity types, more precise span delimitation and further adaptation to real-world hospital documentation.

This clinician-led validation shows that the MS16 systems have moved beyond experimental model comparison and are approaching a level of output quality that clinicians consider useful for hospital-oriented NLP workflows. The Transformers-based system does not yet represent a final deployment-ready

component, but the results show a clear step towards that goal: it extracts clinically meaningful information with substantially higher quality than the initial baseline, while the remaining errors are specific enough to guide targeted refinement. The next development phase will use this feedback to improve context handling, entity boundary detection and label consistency, and to prepare the extracted mentions for terminology normalisation and FHIR-compatible integration within the DataTools4Heart clinical semantic pipeline.

8 Integration into Clinical Semantic Pipeline

The methodologies developed within WP3 are being progressively integrated into a clinical semantic pipeline to enable their use in real-world clinical environments. This integration represents the transition from model development and evaluation to the operational exploitation of multilingual language models and NER systems at clinical sites, where large volumes of clinical text can be processed in a standardised, scalable and interoperable way.

The integration is being carried out through a CogStack-based infrastructure, which provides the orchestration layer connecting local clinical data sources with the NLP components developed in the project. Within this framework, the WP3 models are being incorporated as semantic extraction modules able to process multilingual unstructured clinical narratives and identify relevant clinical information, including diseases, symptoms, procedures, and drugs.

Cogstack orchestrates the automatic running of this pipeline. Once the setup is complete and the final models are deployed, clinical sites only need to place their records (in txt, pdf, docx or xml) in a designated directory. The pipeline then processes incoming documents automatically and outputs structured annotations without further user intervention.

The resulting outputs are being aligned with the broader DataTools4Heart interoperability strategy, with a particular focus on FHIR-compatible representations. In this way, the concepts extracted by the language models and NER systems can be organised as standardised clinical resources, supporting their future use in analytics, cohort characterisation, federated studies, and privacy-preserving research workflows.

In parallel, the pipeline is being prepared to align extracted mentions with clinical terminologies and controlled vocabularies. This terminology alignment will allow recognised entities to be linked to standardised codes, improving semantic interoperability across languages, institutions, and documentation styles.

The integration into the clinical semantic pipeline will allow the WP3 methodologies to be exploited at clinical sites on real-world cardiology data. Through CogStack-based orchestration, FHIR-oriented structuring and terminology alignment, the pipeline is being developed to transform multilingual clinical narratives into structured, semantically enriched, and interoperable data for large-scale reuse within DataTools4Heart.

9 Conclusion and Next Steps

This milestone marks a significant step in the development of multilingual clinical computational semantics and concept recognition systems for cardiology within DataTools4Heart. The work carried out so far has established a complete methodological path from multilingual corpus creation and cardiology-specific language model adaptation to the training, evaluation, and progressive integration of deep learning-based NER systems into clinical semantic pipelines.

Since the beginning of the project, more than 150 models have been trained across languages, model families, training strategies, and entity-recognition configurations. This large-scale experimentation has allowed the consortium to evaluate the contribution of domain-adapted language models, multilingual transformer architectures, cross-validation strategies, and different entity-level modelling approaches. The

current results show that the project has reached a mature development stage in which multilingual clinical NER systems can reliably extract core cardiology-related information, including diseases, symptoms, procedures, and medications, from unstructured clinical narratives.

A key achievement of this milestone is the creation of a strong multilingual foundation for clinical NLP in cardiology. The CardioCCC corpus has enabled the development of comparable NER systems across the seven project languages and has provided a controlled benchmark for evaluating model behaviour across clinical entity types. In parallel, the CardioBERTa model family has demonstrated the value of cardiology-specific language model adaptation, particularly for improving the representation of specialised terminology, clinical expressions, and cardiovascular narrative patterns. Together, these resources constitute an important contribution to European clinical NLP, especially in a multilingual setting where most languages remain underrepresented in existing biomedical AI resources.

The impact of this work goes beyond the development of individual models. The NER systems produced in MS16 provide the semantic extraction layer required to transform free-text EHR narratives into structured clinical information. This is a central requirement for the broader DataTools4Heart objective of enabling interoperable, reusable, and privacy-preserving cardiology data across clinical sites. By producing structured annotations aligned with the project's Common Data Model and FHIR-oriented representations, the work reported in this milestone supports downstream use cases such as cohort characterisation, clinical data harmonization, federated analytics, and large-scale secondary use of real-world cardiovascular data.

At the same time, the milestone also defines the next development phase. Although the current models have been trained mainly on the CardioCCC corpus, WP3 has continued to generate additional multilingual resources in parallel. These new datasets will be used in future deliverables to study how further data expansion, annotation refinement and synthetic or projected resources can improve model performance in the cardiology domain. In this context, the MultiClinAI³³ shared task plays a particularly important role. The task has been launched to promote the development of multilingual clinical entity recognition and annotation projection systems, and has already attracted substantial international participation, with more than 500 submissions and more than 20 participants worldwide. This external benchmarking effort will provide additional evidence on the robustness of the approaches developed in the project and will make it possible to compare DataTools4Heart methodologies against a wider range of systems and modelling strategies.

The next steps will focus on three main technical directions. First, the project will advance from entity recognition to concept normalization. This involves linking the clinical mentions detected by the NER systems to controlled medical terminologies and standard vocabularies, so that extracted entities can be represented not only as text spans but also as interoperable clinical concepts. This step is essential for semantic harmonization across languages, institutions, and documentation styles. It will also require continued work on terminology resources, including the translation or adaptation of ontologies for languages where standardised clinical terminologies are not yet fully available.

Second, the NER and semantic extraction components will be further integrated into the DataTools4Heart federated learning and clinical data infrastructure. As the systems are deployed at clinical sites, the objective is to enable the exploitation of real-world cardiology data while respecting local governance, privacy, and interoperability requirements. The integration through the clinical semantic pipeline will allow NLP-derived annotations to be combined with structured clinical data and reused in federated scenarios without requiring centralisation of sensitive patient-level information.

Third, new versions of the NER models will be developed using the additional resources generated during the project. These future models will exploit expanded multilingual corpora, refined annotations, silver-

³³ <https://temu.bsc.es/MultiClinAI/>

standard datasets, annotation projection outputs and participant systems or code emerging from shared-task activities. This will allow the consortium to evaluate whether larger and more diverse training resources lead to more robust performance across languages, entity types and clinical documentation contexts.

MS16 closes the first implementation cycle of the WP3 clinical concept recognition layer. The work now moves towards the components required for its operational use: linking recognised mentions to clinical terminologies, validating model behaviour on real clinical data, integrating the outputs into federated and FHIR-compatible workflows, and retraining the NER systems with the additional multilingual resources generated during the project. This next phase will make it possible to evaluate not only model performance on benchmark corpora, but also the robustness and usefulness of the extracted information in real cardiology data environments.